

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Statistical Estimation of Lead (Pb) in Groundwater from Smartphone Images of Paper Test Strips using CIEDE2000 Model

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Abstract

Objectives: The propose research work explores an image based data analysis and interpretation approach for detection and estimation of Lead (Pb) in ground water to minimize the human error. It also reviewed the existing traditional techniques which involve chemical analysis or test strips in laboratory. Most of them are expensive, time-consuming and based on human perception. They detect only the presence of the contaminated heavy metals but fail to estimate the amount. **Methods:** This proposed work utilizes images of paper based test strips that are captured by a smartphone camera under ambient lighting condition. The RGB values of the captured images are converted to CIEDELAB color space. Image features were extracted and the perceptual color difference (ΔE) was calculated. Various statistical regression techniques are used to find the correlation between color metrics and the Lead (Pb) concentration. **Findings:** The study suggests that the smartphone-based images can serve as a cost-effective means for on-site heavy-metal screening. Comparative analysis of linear, logarithmic, exponential and quadratic trendlines suggests a consistent relationship between the analyst (Pb) amount and CIEDE2000 value. Based on the improved coefficient of determination (R^2) value, Linear and Quadratic trendline indicates the most supportive relationship between lead (Pb) quantity and CIEDE2000 values. The outcome established the system as a practical alternative under non-uniform lighting conditions in comparison to the conventional RGB-based methods reported in the literature. This approach neither requires any sophisticated instruments or any complex programming algorithms for data analysis. **Novelty:** The study is based on CIEDE2000 perceptual color difference metric unlike relying completely on absolute RGB values or controlled imaging arrangements as done in most of the reported methods in literature. This approach reduces data dependency and improves practical suitability for on field monitoring in resource constrained situation.

Keywords: Feature extraction; Statistical modeling; Regression; Heavy metals; Image Processing

1 Introduction

Ground water contaminated with toxic heavy metals is a serious threat for both the environment as well as to public health. Industrial discharges, improper waste disposal, mining activities are the major carriers of heavy metals such as lead (Pb), arsenic (As), mercury (Hg), cadmium (Cd) to the groundwater. Heavy metals are usually non-biodegradable and tend to accumulate in human body over time⁽¹⁾. On progressive accumulation of Lead in the body may lead to neurological, renal and developmental disorders because of its toxic and non-biodegradable nature⁽²⁾. It necessitates a reliable and sensitive monitoring for on-site water quality. Researchers around the globe are giving priority for the development of a rapid, accurate, low cost and user friendly real time lead (Pb) detection platform.

Conventional Analytical Spectrometric techniques such as atomic fluorescence, atomic absorption, spectrophotometer, and inductively coupled plasma mass and atomic emission are used for heavy metal detection⁽³⁾. These techniques are highly sensitive and accurate and hence very popular among the researchers. But these are not appropriate for field operation or real-time monitoring as the samples are required to transport to the laboratory and expensive instruments and skilled manpower needed for doing the analysis⁽⁴⁾. As a cost effective and sensitive technique, anodic stripping voltammetry (ASV) and potentiometric sensors offer an on-site electrochemical detection of metals⁽⁵⁾. Although these methods have also gained considerable attention, but often found to exhibit limited reproducibility and stability under real time analysis. To overcome these problems, a cost-effective, highly sensitive and selective, user friendly technology with the capability for on-site applications is always in demand. From these perspectives, microfluidic devices like paper test strips are considerably attractive one.

Paper-based test indicators are becoming very popular as a simple, affordable and portable solution for monitoring and detecting various analytes⁽⁶⁾. These sensors leverage the inherent properties of paper, such as its porosity, biodegradability, and ease of chemical modification to create platforms that can rapidly and visually indicate the presence of specific substances⁽⁷⁾. These test indicator sensors can produce measurable signals, often in the form of color changes, which can be interpreted either visually or with the aid of digital tools. Their affordability, convenience in usage, and disposability make them significantly advantageous for applications in resource-limited settings that usually provide simple and visual detection of analytes without complex instruments⁽⁸⁾. From detecting heavy metals in water to identifying pathogens or monitoring environmental pollutants, paper-based sensors hold considerable potentials for foster in point-of-care diagnostics and field based analysis⁽⁹⁾,⁽¹⁰⁾. When they are coupled with smartphone imaging, the system offers an accessible option for rapid field on-site screening.

Yao et al.⁽¹¹⁾, reviewed the use of Paper based test strips across diagnostics and environmental monitoring and also discussed the challenges for practical deployment of it – like insufficient sensitivity, poor quantitative accuracy, high susceptibility to interference of background lighting variations. In⁽¹²⁾, explored paper-based sensors for bacterial detection and its potential in resource limited application. Immanuel et al reported the broad applicability of paper based sensor for monitoring environment and health parameters⁽¹³⁾. In⁽¹⁴⁾, reviewed the application of the real time, non destructive measurement in agricultural field using paper based sensors. The presence of heavy metal ions can be detected with the help of paper sensor and demonstrated the color of such paper sensor got changed when it comes in contact with ions⁽¹⁵⁾. This technique gained significant attention in recent years due to the need of on-field water quality monitoring in places where adequate resources are very limited. However the detection relies mainly on human observation and hence prone to perception error. On integrating the paper based analytical platforms with mobile phone camera imaging, it emerged as a promising alternative for on-site deployment. These reactions typically result in a colorimetric change that can be captured using a mobile camera, and often quantified with the help of a custom mobile app or image-processing algorithm.

In⁽¹⁶⁾, reviewed recent advances in paper-based electrochemical sensors designed for detection of environmental pollutants, outlining the need for real-world environmental monitoring applications. Recently⁽¹⁷⁾, smartphone-based imaging method with improved accuracy and robustness by computing a correction factor which compensate the variations in environmental lighting enabling quantitative iron detection under diverse lighting conditions. It paves a broader smartphone-based colorimetric sensing for point of care applications. A 3D microfluidic paper-based analytical devices (μ PADs) were introduced with improved multiplexing and separation capabilities for simultaneous detection of multiple metals⁽¹⁸⁾. Efforts have been also made to use maleic-acid-capped gold nanoparticles that changes color for improved selectivity. In the work of⁽¹⁹⁾, achieved the on-site quantification using a smartphone — with detection limit of $0.1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The studies however could not address the strategies to compensate for external lighting variability.

Recently, machine learning models are integrated for test strips image analysis to enhance accuracy. For improved interpretation of mobile captured colorimetric data, S. Upadhyay et al. studied extensively the burgeoning smartphone-based sensing paradigms⁽²⁰⁾. Sajed et al. explored to integrate machine learning algorithms with image-based color analysis and develop a Smartphone-based colorimetric sensing platform for the accurate quantification of lead (Pb^{2+}) ions in water⁽²¹⁾.

D. Kim et al. attempted colorimetric color detection using smartphone and used transformation calculation that reduces the influence of the external light sources and enables the acquisition of stable color information⁽²²⁾. Haddout et al. highlighted the potential of smartphones and their built-in sensors, imaging capabilities, and connectivity while collecting and analyzing the water quality⁽²³⁾ and various applications of the model is mentioned in the literature⁽²⁴⁾,⁽²⁵⁾. These studies enhance the prediction accuracy and reduce errors associated with lighting conditions and device variability. With increasing computational power the use of smartphones for image acquisition has become a practical approach. However for image-based analysis the RGB color distances are often not sufficient to quantify subtle changes in color due to lighting conditions, angle, and camera calibration. Advanced color difference models such as CIEDE2000 have shown its potentials for adopting in sensor data analysis. The CIEDE2000 model provides a perceptual measure of color difference under varying lighting conditions incorporating the weighting functions for chroma, lightness, and hue that enhances prediction performance of the model.

It has been observed that PADs coupled with mobile phone cameras represent a transformative step towards democratized environmental monitoring. The primary objective of this research investigation is to develop and validate a systematic methodology to incorporate the CIEDE2000 model for quantifying the lead concentration in ground water. As a secondary objective the work focuses on improving the robustness and accessibility of smartphone-based colorimetry by establishing statistical relationships between image-derived color parameters and known Pb levels, without yet validating against laboratory reference methods. The major contributions of this work include the formulation of a framework based on CIEDE2000 for Pb detection using smartphone-acquired images. It demonstrates a high correlation ($R^2 = 0.97$) between color difference and Pb concentration. The work presents a much less complex alternative to conventional RGB regression and machine learning algorithms, avoiding the need for extensive training datasets and improving the robustness against illumination.

2 Methodology

Lead samples preparation: Standard protocols⁽²⁶⁾ were followed while preparing the Lead solutions with known concentrations. All the glassware were cleaned and rinsed before using in the procedure to avoid any contamination. The setup is allowed to stand for half an hour with intermittent stirring. A stock solution of varying concentration was prepared. After half an hour a few drops of the sample are placed on the market available paper test strips for quality assessment. For higher concentration, Pb ions present in the water bind with the reagent and a visible color change occurs.

Test Strips: Commercially available paper test strips were used as the sensing substrate. All testing experiments were conducted at room temperature under identical conditions. Each test strips were immersed for 30 sec, and then air dried for 1 minute before capturing the image. For each concentration level, each test was repeated four times to ensure repeatability and consistency.

Image Acquisition: The images of the reacted test strips were captured with Motorola 50MP mobile camera under visible light from 15 cm above in a straight position. The camera to sample space and background settings were kept constant while capturing the images.

Image Preprocessing: The test strip images are preprocessed with image enhancement techniques for contrast adjustment. The region of interest (ROIs) of the sensing area of the test strips was selected. Mean RGB values were extracted to minimize the effect of pixel level noise

Feature extraction: Each color of an image is associated with three vectors RGB value, which is a numerical representation of the color. Each color is associated with its respective RGB value. The extracted RGB values of the pixels were calculated and there after converted to the CIELAB color space.. CIE2000 (CIEDE2000) is a color difference formula developed by the International Commission on Illumination (CIE) that measures the perceptual difference between two colors in a more accurate and consistent manner. CIE2000 takes into account the three dimensions of color perception: lightness (L^*), chroma (C^*), and hue (h^*)⁽²⁷⁾. It calculates the color difference (ΔE) by considering the differences in these three dimensions, as well as additional corrections for non-linearities and visual factors.

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta L^*}{k_L S_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta C^*}{k_C S_C}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta H^*}{k_H S_H}\right)^2 + R_T \left(\frac{\Delta C^*}{k_C S_C}\right) \left(\frac{\Delta H^*}{k_H S_H}\right)}$$

where ΔL^* , C^* , and ΔH^* represent the corrected differences in lightness, chroma, and hue, respectively. The weighting functions S_L , S_C , and S_H compensate for perceptual non-uniformities in the CIELAB color space. The parametric factors k_L , k_C and k_H were set to unity under standard imaging conditions. The rotation term R_T accounts for the interaction between chroma and hue differences, improving perceptual accuracy⁽²⁸⁾. Since all images were captured under fixed experimental settings, no additional perceptual scaling factors were introduced.

In this approach all experiments were conducted under identical conditions and measurements for each concentration were repeated four times. The method finally provides numerical ΔE values, showing improvements in sensitivity, objectivity and repeatability in comparison to the conventional testing methods

Fig 1. Methodology flow diagram

3 Results and Discussion

The present study involves the methodological validation using prepared standard Pb solutions. Future work may include validation with laboratory methods like ICP-MS to establish analytical accuracy. The procedure uses paper based Pb detection test strips, combined with a smartphone camera imaging. It leads to portable, low cost and user friendly system without the need for sophisticated instruments.

Most of the reported Smartphone assisted colorimetric detection methods employ RGB or HSV color space for doing analysis of heavy metals in groundwater. RGB intensity based approaches are highly sensitive to camera type and environmental conditions like illumination variations. These lead to less repeatability in results. The present work uses the CIEDE2000 color difference platform which is designed to align with human visual perception and results in improved color discrimination thereby improving the measurement robustness. Measurements were repeated under controlled illumination conditions to ensure reproducibility.

3.1 Colorimetric Response

Based on the RGB values of the test strip images a color index have been created. Lead (Pb^+) Solutions are prepared with known concentration of 0.04ppm, 0.06ppm, 0.08ppm etc. The test strips demonstrated a clear, observable color change upon exposure to lead-contaminated water. At low concentrations ($1 \mu g/L$), the color shift was subtle, while higher concentrations ($50 \mu g/L$) test strip's color changes from beige to shades of pink. The intensity of the color change was consistently observed across multiple trials, indicating the reproducibility of the sensor's response as shown in Figure 2. Each color is associated with its respective RGB value.

Fig 2. Image of the test strip for various Pb solutions

The calculated RGB values are then operated with CIEDE2000 to find the color difference (ΔE). The ΔE values are plotted against 23 different sample images in Figure 3. Figure 4 to Figure 7 are the plot for Lead amount in ppm Vs color difference (ΔE). Various trendlines are used in these plots to capture the underlying relationship and also to find the Coefficient of Determination R^2 for each line. The value of these Coefficients will help to predict the accuracy and can interpret the results more meaningfully.

Table 1. Comparative summary of regression coefficients for different fitting models applied to ΔE against Pb concentration

Function	Different Regression methods			
	Linear	Logarithmic	Exponential	Quadratic
Coefficient of Determination (R^2)	0.9725	0.91816	0.8971	0.9762

Table 1 shows a comparison result in between various Coefficient of Determination (R^2) values. The linear and the quadratic regression line show the best fit relation through the data series which can be used to predict the Lead amount from the calculated color difference (ΔE) of a lead test strip image. As can be observed in Table 2, the comparative evaluation of linear and quadratic regression models both provide a comparable calibration performance (quadratic model exhibited slightly

Fig 3. Calculated ΔE for each sample image as the concentration of Pb increases

Fig 4. Linear regression analysis between color difference (ΔE_{00}) and Pb concentration with strong correlation ($R^2 = 0.9725$)

reduced prediction error with RMSE = 0.00205 compared to the linear model with RMSE = 0.00220). To assess the predictive robustness both linear and quadratic models were analysed using Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOOCV), which shows minimal difference between training and cross-validation. It confirms that none of these two models suffers from overfitting. The improved predictive performance by the quadratic model suggests mild non-linearity in the concentration- ΔE relationship.

Table 2. Comparative summary of performance metrics for the linear and quadratic models correlating ΔE and Pb concentration

Model	R ²	RMSE	MAE	Intercept	Linear Coefficient (ΔE)	R ² CV (LOOCV)	RMSECV (LOOCV)
Linear	0.9725	0.00220	0.00178	0.04383	-0.000265	0.9658	0.00261
Quadratic	0.9762	0.00205	0.00163	0.04507	-0.000331	0.9674	0.00239

Fig 5. Logarithmic regression analysis between color difference (ΔE_{00}) and Pb concentration with correlation ($R^2 = 0.91816$)

Fig 6. Exponential regression analysis between color difference (ΔE_{00}) and Pb concentration with correlation ($R^2 = 0.8971$)

Fig 7. Quadratic regression analysis between color difference (ΔE_{00}) and Pb concentration with correlation ($R^2 = 0.9762$)

The reported existing methods often focus on instrument-based methods that prioritize sensitivity at the cost of accessibility or on simple test-strips which lack quantitative analysis. As reported by Sajed et al Sajed the machine learning algorithms can be used to improve quantitative accuracy⁽²¹⁾; but requires extensive training and computational resources. Most of the detection methods like Solhtalab et al. (2025) as demonstrated for Pb²⁺ and Cd²⁺ detection in⁽¹⁶⁾, suffers from subjective human perception and also sensitive to environmental conditions. In contrast the proposed approach fills this gap between simplicity and quantitative reliability by employing a perceptually uniform CIEDE2000 color analysis, reducing dimensional complexity and enhancing interpretability while maintaining strong linear correlation. This makes this approach as computationally simple alternative for field-deployable Pb monitoring.

However interference from other metal ions, variability in strip fabrication, and aging-related degradation of chromatic reagents present in the strips may be considered as probable sources of variability. While this study utilized prepared standard Pb solutions under controlled conditions, real environmental samples may effects influencing color response. Future work needed for systematically evaluate the interference from ions such as Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, and Zn²⁺ and analyse long-term strip stability under storage conditions.

4 Conclusion

The available paper sensors in the market exhibits detection limit of approximately 5 µg/L of Pb, which is well below the allowable concentration in drinking water as per international standards (e.g., 10 µg/L by the WHO and the EPA). This makes the sensor highly sensitive and suitable for environmental monitoring.

Quadratic as well as linear regression provides an accurate model relating the CIEDE2000 data series of the Lead (Pb⁺) test strip images with the Lead (Pb⁺) amount in the contaminated water. These findings support the possibility of using perceptual color difference as a substitute for estimating Pb levels.

The previous works have reported the potential of smartphone-based color analysis for Pb²⁺ detection, however this study demonstrated the possibility of CIEDE2000-based colorimetric framework for smartphone-based Pb detection using prepared standard solutions. The observed dependency of ΔE on Pb concentration supports its application for semi-quantitative estimation and screening. The proposed CIEDE2000 framework reduces computational overhead and also improves perceptual consistency as compared to RGB-intensity regression and machine learning based models. This approach relies on a standardized color difference metric unlike the ML approaches which based on large datasets and device specific parameters, thus making it suitable for resource-constrained and field-deployable applications.

Although the proposed approach offers a cost effective, computationally simple, and field-deployable alternative for preliminary Pb assessment, further validation against laboratory reference methods is required to establish absolute quantitative accuracy. However factors such as camera sensor variation and strip aging could introduce systematic errors in the procedure. Moreover present results are limited to statistical consistency within the dataset only so future work may focus on external validation, inter-device calibration, and interference studies with competing metal ions.

This framework is particularly suitable in resource-limited fields, rural water monitoring, and rapid environmental risk screening, where conventional instrumentation may not be available.

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